

Studies with Model Membranes : Evaluation of the Thermodynamically Effective Fixed Charge Density and Test of the Theories of Membrane Potential and Bi-ionic Potential Based on Thermodynamics of Irreversible Processes

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Manuscript received 13 June 1978, revised 30 July 1979, accepted 31 December 1979

Membrane potentials and bi-ionic potentials across two parchment supported Cobalt and Chromium orthovanadate membranes using various 1:1 electrolytes have been reported. Theoretical equations based on thermodynamics of irreversible processes for membrane potentials and bi-ionic potentials, derived recently by Nagasawa *et al* and Toyoshima and Nozaki have been applied to derive the thermodynamically effective fixed charge density which is an important parameter governing the membrane phenomena and other membrane parameters. The derived membrane parameters have been used to predict bi-ionic potentials across the membranes. Theoretical predictions were borne out quite satisfactorily by our experimental results.

THERMODYNAMICALLY effective fixed charge density which is an important parameter governing the membrane phenomena has been one of the most widely characterized electrochemical and bio-electric phenomena. Based on the fixed charge concept^{1,2} a number of mathematically rigorous equations for membrane potential have in recent years, been derived³⁻⁶ and their validity examined by taking model membrane systems⁷⁻¹⁵. Most recently Nagasawa and coworkers¹⁶⁻¹⁷ as well as Toyoshima and Nozaki¹⁸ have derived equations for membrane potential utilizing the principles of non-equilibrium thermodynamics⁶. In this paper we describe a series of electric potentials observed across cobalt and chromium orthovanadate membranes separating various 1:1 electrolytes at different concentrations for the evaluation of effective fixed charge density of the membranes utilizing the recently developed equations for membrane potential. An effort has been made to examine the validity of the equations developed.

Experimental

Preparation of Membranes :

Cobalt and Chromium orthovanadate membranes were prepared by the method of interaction suggested by Siddiqi Beg and coworkers⁷⁻¹⁵.

The electrochemical cell of the type

Reference electrode	Solution C ₁	Membrane	Solution C ₂	reference electrode
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was used for measuring electrical potentials arising across the membrane by maintaining a ten fold difference in concentration (i.e. $C_2/C_1=10$) and using a Pye Precision Vernier Potentiometer (No. 7568). The bi-ionic potentials were determined by taking two electrolytes of the type AP and BP of the same concentration in place of the solutions C₁ and C₂. The salt solutions (Chloride of K⁺, Na⁺ and NH₄⁺) were prepared from analytical grade reagent (B.D.H.) using deionized water.

Results and Discussion

When two electrolyte solutions of different concentrations are separated by a membrane, mobile species penetrate the membrane and various transport phenomena are induced in the system. The fixed charge concept of Teorell-Meyer-Sievers is the pertinent starting point for investigation of actual mechanisms of transport of molecular or ionic processes in the membrane phase. The theory has been generally accepted and widely used for the evaluation of membrane parameters using potentiometric method. Recently Nagasawa *et al*^{16,17}, based on the theory of irreversible processes, have derived equation for membrane potential. The total membrane potential $\Delta\phi_m$ was considered as the sum of diffusion potential $\Delta\phi_d$ inside the membrane and the electrostatic potential difference $\Delta\phi_e$ between the membrane surfaces and electrolyte solutions on both sides of the membrane. These authors derived the

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following equation for membrane potential

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\Delta\phi_m = & \frac{RT}{F} \left(\frac{\bar{x}}{2} \right) \left(\frac{\sigma^- - 1}{\sigma^-} \right) \frac{1}{C'} + \frac{RT}{F} \frac{U_+ - U_-}{U_+ + U_-} \\
 & \times \left[\frac{1 - \frac{XJ_0}{RTC_0(U_+ - U_-)k}}{1 - \frac{XJ_0}{2RTC_0U_+K}} \right] \ln \sigma^- \\
 & + \frac{RT}{2F} \frac{X}{U_+U_-} \frac{J_0}{RTC_0K} \left[\frac{1 - \frac{XJ_0(U_+ + U_-)}{4RTC_0U_+U_-K}}{1 - \frac{XJ_0}{2RTC_0U_+K}} \right] (\sigma^- - 1)C'
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

At sufficiently high electrolyte concentrations eq. (1) was approximated to

$$\Delta\phi_m = \frac{RT}{F} (\sigma^- - 1/\sigma^-) (\bar{x}/2)/C' + \dots \tag{2}$$

This equation predicts a linear relationship between membrane potential $\Delta\phi_m$ and $1/C'$. The values of

$\Delta\phi_m$ [Table 1] were plotted against $1/C'$. A set of straight lines in Figs. 1 and 2 point towards the correctness of the theory. The values of \bar{x} were calculated from the slope of the lines and are given in Table 2. The values are quite low which is in agreement with our earlier findings of diffusion rate studies.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\Delta\phi_m(\sigma^- - 1)/\sigma^-$ vs $1/C'$ for various electrolytes with Chromium orthovanadate membrane.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\phi_m(\sigma^- - 1)/\sigma^-$ vs $1/C'$ for various electrolytes with Cobalt orthovanadate membrane.

TABLE 1—MEMBRANE POTENTIALS mV OBTAINED THROUGH CHROMIUM AND COBALT ORTHOVANADATE MEMBRANES

Concentrations (eq/l)	Chromium orthovanadate			Cobalt orthovanadate		
	KCl	NaCl	NH ₄ Cl	KCl	NaCl	NH ₄ Cl
1/0.1	7.85	-5.05	3.06	15.55	0.60	3.80
0.5/0.05	13.52	-1.82	7.22	22.34	3.15	8.00
0.1/0.01	18.70	18.45	23.65	26.75	20.80	25.72
0.05/0.005	24.10	28.05	30.25	29.20	27.82	31.35
0.01/0.001	29.35	32.85	34.45	32.50	31.40	35.00
0.005/0.0005	31.05	34.05	35.10	34.00	32.95	34.45
0.001/0.0001	32.25	34.35	35.29	35.55	34.15	35.95

TABLE 2—DERIVED VALUES OF THE MOBILITY RATIO (U_+/U_-), CHARGE DENSITY (\bar{x}) OF CHROMIUM AND COBALT ORTHOVANADATE BY TMS AND NAGASAWA METHOD.

Electrolytes	Chromium orthovanadate			Cobalt orthovanadate		
	TMS Method		Nagasawa Method	TMS Method		Nagasawa Method
	U_+/U_-	Xeq/lit	Xeq/lit	U_+/U_-	Xeq/lit	Xeq/lit
KCl	1.20	1.778×10^{-3}	1.784×10^{-3}	1.00	6.309×10^{-3}	1.779×10^{-3}
NaCl	0.80	2.511×10^{-3}	3.662×10^{-3}	0.80	3.981×10^{-3}	3.192×10^{-3}
NH ₄ Cl	1.00	2.818×10^{-3}	3.202×10^{-3}	1.00	3.548×10^{-3}	3.202×10^{-3}

Most recently Toyoshima and Nozaki¹⁸ derived theoretical equations for membrane potential and bi-ionic potential using certain crucial assumptions for mobility and activity coefficients of ions within the membrane. The theoretical equation for BIP was

$$\Delta\phi_{BIP} = 2 \ln(K_A/K_B) + \ln(JV_A + 1)/(JV_B + 1) \left(\frac{F}{RT} \right) \quad (3)$$

where the symbol K_A/K_B is called the selectivity constant for + ion species. The flux J and the membrane

Fig. 3. Plots of $1/t_{app}^-$ vs $1/C$ for Chromium orthovanadate membrane.

Fig. 4. Plots of $1/t_{app}^-$ vs $1/C$ for Cobalt orthovanadate membrane.

parameters V_N and \bar{X}/K_N were expressed as follows

$$V_N = 1 + U_N^0/U_P^0 \quad (N=A, B) \quad (4)$$

$$(2J + 1) \ln(gA + 2J)/(gB + 2J) - \ln(JV_A + 1)/(JV_B + 1) - \ln(gA/gB) = 0 \quad (5)$$

and

$$g_N = 1 + \sqrt{1 + (2K_N C/X)^2} \quad (6)$$

In order to derive the values of V_N and \bar{X}/K_N , Toyoshima and Nozaki have derived another expression (eq. 7).

$$\frac{1}{t_-} = V_N + (V_N - 1)(\sigma - 1)/\sigma \ln \sigma (\bar{X}/K_N)(1/C_N) + \dots \quad (7)$$

When the transference number t_- was defined by the Nernst eqn.

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{RT}{F} (1 - 2t_-) \ln \sigma \quad (8)$$

The values of V_N and \bar{X}/K_N were obtained from the intercept and slope of the linear plots of $1/t_-$ vs $1/C_N$. The

TABLE 3—DERIVED VALUES OF PARAMETERS \bar{X}/K_N , V_N OF CHROMIUM AND COBALT ORTHOVANADATE MEMBRANE USING VARIOUS ELECTROLYTES.

Membranes	Electrolytes	Parameters	
		\bar{X}/K_N	V_N
Chromium orthovanadate	KCl	0.28	2.28
	NaCl	0.34	2.07
	NH ₄ Cl	0.53	2.00
Cobalt orthovanadate	KCl	0.38	2.58
	NaCl	0.36	1.95
	NH ₄ Cl	0.45	2.05

TABLE 4—DERIVED VALUES OF g_N (N=KCl, NaCl, NH₄Cl) ACROSS CHROMIUM AND COBALT ORTHOVANADATE MEMBRANES.

Membrane Concentration (eq/lit)	Chromium orthovanadate			Cobalt orthovanadate		
	g_{k+}	g_{Na+}	g_{NH_4+}	g_{k+}	g_{Na+}	g_{NH_4+}
0.5	4.709	4.107	3.135	3.820	3.952	3.437
0.1	2.229	2.160	2.069	2.130	2.144	2.094
0.05	2.062	2.042	2.018	2.034	2.038	2.024
0.01	2.003	2.002	2.001	2.001	2.002	2.001
0.005	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000
0.001	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000

values of V_N and \bar{X}/K_N thus derived were then used in eq (6) to get the values for g_N . Finally the value of the flux J was calculated using eq (5). Once

Fig. 5. Plots of observed (—) and calculated (---) bi-ionic potentials $\Delta\psi$ vs log C for different pairs of electrolytes with Chromium orthovanadate membrane.

Fig. 6. Plots of observed (—) and calculated (---) bi-ionic potentials $\Delta\phi$ vs log C for different pairs of electrolytes with Cobalt orthovanadate membrane.

the membrane parameters J , V_N , \bar{X}/K_N , gN are known, one can calculate theoretical bi-ionic potential using eq.(3). The theoretical bi-ionic potentials thus calculated

were plotted as a function of C_N in Figs. 5 and 6. The observed bi-ionic potentials were also plotted in the same graphs. Figs. 5 and 6 demonstrate that the theoretical predictions are borne out quite satisfactorily by our experimental results. However, a little deviation may be due to various reasons most notably due to the different degree of ionic interactions with the membrane skeleton at different electrolyte concentrations.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. W. Rahman, Head, Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh for providing the necessary research facilities and also to C.S.I.R. (India) for the award of fellowships to Badrul Islam and Akmal Husain.

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